

Overview of CODATA Activities and Achievements

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Status and Purpose of this Document

This document provides a summary of current and recent CODATA activities and achievements. It is intended to inform CODATA members and to be circulated prior to the (Virtual) General Assembly to be held on 15-16 November 2021.

CODATA's Mission and Strategy

CODATA's [mission](#) is to connect data and people to advance science and improve our world.

As the Committee on Data of the [International Science Council \(ISC\)](#), CODATA helps realise ISC's vision of advancing science as a global public good. CODATA does this by promoting international collaboration to advance Open Science and to improve the availability and usability of data for all areas of research. CODATA supports the principle that data produced by research and susceptible to be used for research should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. CODATA works also to advance the interoperability and the usability of such data: research data should be [FAIR \(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable\)](#).

In its Strategic Plan, CODATA presents its activities in four priority areas¹:

1. Decadal Programme: Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges
2. Data Policy
3. Data Science
4. Data Skills

1: Decadal Programme: Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges

CODATA has been entrusted to contribute to the [ISC's Action Plan 2019-2021](#) in two specific and related areas ([Making Data Work...](#) and [Open Science](#)). These are combined below in the strategic mission to develop an international, decade-long programme to facilitate interoperability and reusability of data for cross-domain research and to encourage co-operation, alignment and interoperability between national and regional Open Science initiatives.

The activities are presented in three sections below: 1) Core Interoperability Framework; 2) Cross-Domain Case Studies; and 3) the Global Open Science Cloud Initiative.

¹ A draft updated Strategic Plan 2022-25 is in preparation and an outline will be discussed at the (Virtual) General Assembly 2021.

Core Interoperability Framework

Through a number of activities, CODATA has been exploring the components of a Core Interoperability Framework. This is a work in progress and comprises 1) the collaboration with the Data Documentation Initiative on DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration); 2) work on FAIR vocabularies; 3) work on provenance; and, 4) work on Digital Representation of Units of Measure.

DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration)

[DDI-CDI](#) is a model driven, domain and technology neutral metadata specification designed to facilitate the combination of data from diverse sources and across disciplines. The draft specification was released in 2020 and the first production ready specification will be released in early 2022. The development was influenced by the series of [Workshops at Schloss Dagstuhl](#) on Interoperability of Metadata Standards in Cross-Domain Science held in collaboration between the DDI Alliance and CODATA.

DDI-CDI provides a systematic way to describe i) a set of common data structures (tabular data, time-series data, multi-dimensional data, key-value (Big) data); ii) the relation between measurements (individual 'datums'), variables and concepts (the variable cascade); and, iii) provenance and processing (using a process model and an implementation of PROV-O). The DDI-CDI specification thus facilitates the decombination and recombination of data at a granular level and the machine actionability of these processes. It is designed to work with other metadata schema and with various semantic artefacts (vocabularies and ontologies).

DDI-CDI Webinar Series, 2020-21

CODATA collaborated on a [series of webinars](#), workshops and conference sessions about DDI-CDI to encourage feedback and explore applications. This work contributed substantively to the further development of DDI-CDI and to the identification of case studies.

The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Possible Uses and Applications, April 2021

CODATA undertook a co-creation project for the EOSC secretariat to explore the uses and applications of DDI-CDI in EOSC. The main output was a substantial report, [‘The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Possible Uses and Applications’](#), that explores a number of use cases and the relation of DDI-CDI to the FAIR ecosystem. A [launch workshop was held on 11 June 2021](#) with the objective of publicising the report and further identifying cross-domain use cases for inclusion in future work. As a result case studies are being explored in a wide range of research areas and with a number of research infrastructures, including the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration, NSD and EOSC Future, ENVRI-FAIR, UKDA and EuroStat. Four of these case studies were explored during the 2021 (hybrid) Dagstuhl Workshop [‘2021 Interoperability for Cross-Domain Research: Use Cases for Metadata Standards’](#) (27 Sept-1 Oct). These case studies were also presented at Virtual SciDataCon 2021 session [‘DDI-CDI: The Challenge of Cross-Domain Data Integration’](#).

DDI-CDI and FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)

The [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#) report remarks on the importance of DDI-CDI in general and specifically in relation to FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). It is easy to see that DDI-CDI can provide some of the core information necessary for the processing of FDOs. A session was held at the [FAIR Festival 21-23 June](#) on '[The Relationship of FAIR Data Objects and Metadata in The FAIR Ecosystem: Questions and Considerations from the DDI-CDI Perspective](#)' to explore this topic.

Cross-Domain Workshops 2021

Following feedback and refinements, the first production release of DDI-CDI will be made in early 2022. A series of workshops were organised in September 2021. Week one (20-24 Sept, Dagstuhl and hybrid) focused on '[Further Development of the DDI Cross Domain Integration Model for FAIR Data Sharing across Discipline and Domain Boundaries](#)', including the incorporation of further data structures. Week two (27 Sept-1 Oct), already mentioned above, looked at [Use Cases](#), and was organised in parallel with a virtual Australian workshop on [FAIR vocabularies](#).

FAIR Vocabularies

One of the outcomes of the 2019 Dagstuhl Workshop was a small group led by Simon Cox that produced the paper [Ten Simple Rules for making a vocabulary FAIR](#). Relatedly, a series of workshop and conference sessions have been held on the topic, most notably at the [FAIR Convergence Symposium](#) at the NISO conference and elsewhere. and at [Virtual SciDataCon 2021](#). Further papers on other aspects of FAIR vocabulary development and management are underway or planned. A comprehensive double session '[Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability](#)' was also organised at [Virtual SciDataCon 2021](#), looking at the status and implementation in various domains, good practice in the maintenance, governance and sustainability of vocabularies, and seeking to further refine and clarify the technical requirements.

[IUSSP-CODATA Working Group on FAIR Vocabularies](#)

A joint International Union for the Scientific Study of Populations and CODATA WG, chaired by George Alter, is now applying the 'Ten Simple Rules' to a set of vocabularies in demographics and population sciences. Participants include representatives of UN Stats, OECD, and various national agencies and projects concerned with maintaining core vocabularies.

Other Applications of Good Practice for FAIR Vocabularies

CODATA, with partners where necessary, will also apply these good practices to other vocabularies, including the [UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles](#), the [CASRAI Research Data Management Terminology](#) and [Terms4FAIRskills](#).

FAIR Vocabularies Next Steps

Two avenues of work are being explored, to build on the FAIR Vocabularies paper and the series of workshops. 1) A landscape survey and good practice guide for the maintenance, governance and sustainability of vocabularies. 2) In the Virtual SciDataCon session, a call was made to apply the approach and methodology taken by the IUSSP-CODATA WG to other domains and with other international scientific unions and associations. Discussions are already under way to explore how this may be taken forward with the assistance of the International Science Council.

Provenance

Reliable and rich provenance and processing information is essential to Interoperability and Reusability. [PROV-O](#) (the W3C provenance ontology) provides a basis, but is very general and more detailed and specific implementations are needed (DDI-CDI features such an implementation which will need further refinement). Two conference workshops were held [to survey technical implementations \(FAIR Convergence Symposium, Dec 2020\)](#) and [the approach to provenance taken in a range of domains \(RDA P17, April 2021\)](#).

Provenance Next Steps

[Discussions are underway about next steps](#), with a view to exploring provenance issues and implementations in various domains / case studies and ultimately leading to a more sophisticated cross-domain implementation of PROV-O (i.e. an implementation that can carry more information but remains sufficiently generic to be used as a basis for provenance in different domains). *This work is important but remains in an early stage: there has not yet been sufficient capacity to prioritise it.*

[DRUM \(Digital Representation of Units of Measure\) Task Group](#)

The consistent digital (and FAIR) representation of units is fundamental to Interoperability and Reusability of data. The DRUM Task Group aims to clarify the complex landscape, contribute to improvement cooperation and alignment across various initiatives and make recommendations for good practice. Outputs to date include:

- [Units of Measure for Humans and Machines](#) (a manifesto and call to action): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081656>
- The TG has recruited 'Ambassadors' from 27 International Scientific Unions, with whom two workshops have been held ([First Briefing Session, 1 October 2020](#); [FAIR Convergence Symposium Workshop, 3 December 2020](#))
- Presentations at the BIPM Workshop ['The International System of Units \(SI\) in FAIR Digital Data'](#)
- A survey of practice in relation to units in different domains, gathering information from the Ambassadors.
- Session at Virtual SciDataCon 2021 ['Improving our World One Unit at a Time'](#)

DRUM Next Steps

The next steps for the TG will be to develop reports/publications on the following topics:

- Landscape of different unit annotations and services (draft underway)
- Current practices in the representation of units in diverse research domains (based on the survey)

The DRUM TG is an important link to the [BIPM](#), with which [CODATA concluded an MOU on 11 October 2021](#), and the [Digital SI initiative](#), to other systems for representing units, and to the ISUs. The CODATA DRUM TG is collaborating on the Digital SI through quarterly meetings of the CIPM's Digital SI Expert Group and CODATA DRUM. CODATA and ISC are also contributing to the development of a Joint Statement of Intent: On the digital transformation in the international scientific and quality infrastructure.

Core Interoperability Next Steps

Planning is already underway for the 2022 Dagstuhl Workshops. A significant focus of these and preceding work will be describing the core components of interoperability and making recommendations about their use or further work. The CODATA Executive Director has been appointed to the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force, where these issues will also be explored through a number of case studies. Finally, the World FAIR proposal, if funded, will explore the emerging core interoperability framework with a set of domain and cross-domain case studies drawn from CODATA and RDA partners around the world.

Cross-Domain Case Studies

Through the Dagstuhl Workshops and other activities, a number of Cross-Domain Case Studies have been developed.

Infectious Diseases: INSPIRE and INSPIRE-PEACH

CODATA has been a partner with the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) and the African Population and Health Research Centre (APHRC) on the [INSPIRE](#) project, which combines demographic health data and clinical data, principally in relation to HIV then in relation to COVID. A case study was included in the [Report on 'The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Possible Uses and Applications'](#) and the project was presented at the [FAIR Convergence Symposium](#) and at [Virtual SciDataCon 2021](#). The reports on [INSPIRE Data Hub: Technical Results of Phase 1](#) are now available.

INSPIRE-PEACH continues this work more fully in the direction of COVID, adding genomic data to the mix. Key technical components include OMOP and related vocabularies, DDI-CDI, and the work done by VODAN on the WHO COVID reporting form. It is hoped that this will become a major case study in combining data and will allow links with related work in Europe and elsewhere.

Healthy and Resilient Cities

Because of the challenges they face and because of the capacity to gather data in urban environments, cities represent an excellent test bed for data interoperability and reusability. CODATA has a number of activities looking at data for healthy, smart and resilient cities.

Healthy and Resilient Cities WG

Combining participants in a number of past events, including Dagstuhl Workshops, [Resilience Brokers](#), the [ISC Programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing](#), CODATA has maintained a WG on Healthy and Resilient Cities to explore collaborations in this area. The current focus is on developing a methodology for Data-Knowledge-Action Systems (DAKAS).

A workshop exploring this in the context of green space, using Guangzhou as a first case study was held 21-25 June 2021. The outcomes of this work were presented in a report and at a Virtual SciDataCon session on [‘Collaborative Systems Modelling for Urban Health’](#).

Relatedly, work has been suggested to explore the issue of data and indicators, building on work in India (National Institute of Urban Affairs) and Australia. CODATA has also developed a valuable partnership with SALURBAL, the major research programme on urban health in Latin America, led by Drexel University.

Smart Cities TG

The [Data Integration and Data Science for Urban Life and Smart Cities TG](#) engages with the above activities, while also pursuing its own mission. Key outputs include a special issue on [‘Smart, Sustainable and Fair Cities’](#) in the Geography Research Forum journal.

Achievements include:

- Special track [‘Mobility as a Service \(MaaS\) and the Design Challenge of Inclusion, Sustainability, and Data Ownership’](#) at the ‘Data for Policy Conference, University College London (UCL), 14-16 September 2021.
- Training materials and curriculum ‘Transitioning to Smart City Growth’, comparing cities between tradition and innovation, developed for a Smart Cities summer course will now be incorporated in a new M.A. program in Smart Cities and Urban Informatics, Jerusalem.

Smart and Resilient Cities: CODATA Connect Early Career Group

In 2020 the [CODATA Connect Early Career Group](#) ran a very successful series of seven webinars on topics relating to [Smart and Resilient Cities](#). Many of the speakers were drawn from the two activities listed above. This was followed by a podcast series [‘Data for Resilient Cities’](#), in partnership with CEPT University Center for Applied Geomatics. This is being followed by a further podcast series for 2021 in partnership with the ISC Programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing, [exploring the DAKAS methodology](#). The CODATA Connect group was also involved in a number of smart cities related sessions at the [FAIR Convergence Symposium](#). Finally, the CODATA Connect Group is planning a (virtual or hybrid) workshop on Open Data Policies for Urban Governments (date to be confirmed).

Disaster Risk Reduction and SDGs

Various of the activities above touch on DRR and the SDGs (e.g. SDG Target 3.3 Communicable Diseases; SDG Target 11.3 Inclusive and sustainable urbanization). Some of these were summarised in a UN Data Forum Session in 2020 [‘Multi-Stakeholder Data Bridges: making data work for cross-domain grand challenges’](#), which brought together the technical concerns and the case studies mentioned above. CODATA was invited to report on further progress at the UN Data Forum in 2021 with the session [‘Multi-Stakeholder Data Bridges II: making data work for cross-domain grand challenges’](#).

UNDRR/ISC Hazard Information Profiles

The [UNDRR/ISC Hazard Information Profiles](#) are a supplement to the [UNDRR/ISC Hazard Definition & Classification Review: Technical Report \(2020\)](#). The Technical Working Group was chaired by Virginia Murray, Head of Global Disaster Risk Reduction, UK Health Security Agency and a member of the CODATA Executive Committee. As discussed in the [UN World Data Forum Session on ‘Multi-Stakeholder Data Bridges II – Making data work for cross-domain grand challenges’](#), held on 4 October, CODATA will now be working to make the HIPs into a FAIR Vocabulary, following the guidelines laid down in the article [Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR](#).

[FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research TG](#)

This is a relatively long-standing Task Group that recently changed its name to emphasise a new focus on FAIR data. Recent outputs and achievements include:

- [DRR White Papers 2017-2020](#): covering topics such as a gap analysis on data connectivity and a survey of next-generation disaster data infrastructure.
- Series of [DRR Webinars](#), in partnership with Tonkin+Taylor.
- [DRR and Open DATA newsletter](#), monthly newsletter with over 1000 subscribers.
- [GEO SDG Testimonial Award for work on Rapid Damage Mapping Response](#) in recognition of a number of occasions on which the TG has helped provide [rapid disaster data responses](#) (see notably the [letter of thanks from the New Zealand Government](#)).

FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research TG: Next Steps

The TG is currently working on a series of [Policy Briefs](#), the first of which [‘Are we there yet? The transition from response to recovery for the COVID-19 pandemic’](#) appeared during the pandemic.

The TG has proposed a session [Make it count: Harnessing risk-based data for disaster and climate resilience](#) for SciDataCon/IDW.

[CODATA-WDS TG on Citizen Science for the SDGs](#)

This jointly-convened TG has been very active and has been imaginative in using its resources to fund two interns who have assisted with the work. The main outputs have been:

- A series of [How To Guides for Citizen Science Groups on SDG Indicators](#), covering SDG Indicators 3.1.1 Maternal Mortality; 11.6.1 Municipal solid waste; 15.5.1 Red List Index; 13.1.2 Adoption and implementation of national disaster risk reduction strategies.
- A series of articles on Citizen Science and the SDGs
 - Bowser, A, et al. (2020) “Still in Need of Norms: The State of the Data in Citizen Science” in Citizen Science: Theory and Practice <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.303>
 - de Sherbinin et Al. (2021). “The Critical Importance of Data to Citizen Science” in Frontiers in Climate <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.650760>

- A survey of Citizen Science data activities in Africa (not yet published but the topic of a [FAIR Convergence Symposium session 'Citizen Science Generated Data in Africa and Potential Contribution to SDGs'](#)).

Citizen Science for the SDGs: Next Steps

The TG will produce:

- A report on Aligning Citizen Generated Data with the UN SDG Indicators in Africa
- Catalogue of citizen science generated data projects and contribute the database to an African repository and SciStarter
- A session on 'Bridging Service Gaps: UN Sustainable Development Goals and Guidelines for CS Generated Data in Developing Countries' has been proposed for International Data Week in Seoul, 2022.

Task Group on Agriculture Data, Knowledge for Learning and Innovation

The [TG on Agriculture Data, Knowledge for Learning and Innovation](#) also contributes to CODATA work on data for the SDGs. The main activities have been to develop a data platform for data integration and analysis at KALRO, the Kenyan Agriculture and Livestock Research Institute. This has been supported by technical workshops and training activities. The TG convened a session at the FAIR Convergence Symposium on '[Role of Data Stewardship Centres in Research Institutions: The Case of Kenya Market Information Systems and Livestock Market Information System](#)'. The TG organised a session at Virtual SciDataCon on '[Making Open Data Work for Small Scale Farmers: A Case for Developing Countries](#)'.

Global Open Science Cloud Initiative

The [Global Open Science Cloud \(GOSC\) initiative](#) aims to encourage cooperation, alignment and interoperability, between various regional and national Open Science Clouds or Platforms. A launch [event was held on 28 June to provide information about the initiative and to invite participation in the Working Groups and Case Studies](#).

GOSC is now pursuing its activities through [thematic Working Groups](#) addressing a number of challenges shared by Open Science Clouds. These include:

- Governance and Sustainability: sharing experiences and good practice.
- Policy and Legal Dimensions: aligning principles, policies and exploring legal issues.
- Technical Infrastructure: including network connectivity and protocols, secure Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), mechanisms for federation of computing, data and other services.
- Semantic Interoperability: including identifiers, semantic services, rigorous contextual and provenance metadata, analytical tools and virtual research environments.

GOSC will also develop [Case Studies of domain and cross-domain research supported by different Open Science infrastructures](#). Five initial Case Studies are underway:

- Incoherent scatter radar data;
- Diffraction data;
- Ecology and biodiversity data;
- Data for SDG13 climate change and disaster risk reduction;
- Population health data.

Sessions on the [Working Groups](#) and [Case Studies](#) were organised for Virtual SciDataCon 2021.

Initial support comes from CODATA and a CAS funded project at CNIC. A CODATA-CNIC International Programme Office is being established at CNIC to support GOSC and other aspects of the Decadal Programme. We aim also to expand and diversify the GOSC partners: for example, the Malaysian Academy of Sciences/MOSP has indicated interest in taking an active role in the case study on biodiversity data. The WGs and CSs are holding regular meetings to develop their work plan. CODATA is providing a [Confluence workspace](#) to support the initiative.

In parallel, the [Open Science Commons Executives' Roundtable \(OSCER\)](#) has been established, jointly chaired by George Strawn and Jean-Claude Burgelman. The first meeting was held on 30 June. CODATA is providing secretariat support. OSCER will act as an independent body, with its own agenda, but is invited to advise GOSC.

2: Data Policy

CODATA has a long history of work in the data policy area, contributing substantively—for example—to the [2007 OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding](#). CODATA has produced [a series of significant data policy reports](#) since 2015.

International Data Policy Committee

The principal means by which CODATA acts in the data policy arena is through the [International Data Policy Committee](#). The IDPC acts in a number of ways:

- Providing expertise for ad hoc and timely response to data policy matters:
 - the most recent example is [Open Science for a Global Transformation: CODATA-coordinated submission to the UNESCO Open Science Consultation \(2020\)](#)
- Developing its own activities and subgroups:
 - the most recent example is the [Beijing Declaration on Research Data](#) and the related [Workshop on Open Research Data Policy and Practice](#) (Sept 2019)
- Leveraging expertise for funded work:
 - the most recent example is the independent [CODATA Twenty-Year Review of GBIF \(2020\)](#)

International Data Policy Committee: Next Steps

IDPC Subgroups

Historically the IDPC has had a number of subgroups, including data diplomacy, public and private sector data. The IDPC is currently reviewing its subgroups, but current activities and discussions point towards:

- Data Diplomacy Framework (and relating this to SDGs and to GOSC)
- Data Rights and Responsibilities
- Data Policy Training
- Sensitive Data

Independent Review of CASEarth

Using the same methodology as the review of GBIF, CODATA is conducting an independent review of the data policy of CASEarth, as large EO and SDG research infrastructure. The project team is Paul Uhler (former IDPC chair), Bob Samors (former GEO), LI Aitong (previously consultant on the GBIF review).

Executive Director Data Policy Activities

Some of CODATA's data policy activities have been undertaken through contribution of Executive Director effort. The most significant pieces of work in recent years are:

- [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), as vice chair of the Expert Advisory Committee (2020-2021).
- [Turning FAIR into Reality](#), as chair of the EC's High Level Expert Group (2017-2018).

3: Data Science

CODATA seeks to advance the frontiers of data science in relation to the use of data in all fields of research. The primary mechanisms are the Data Science Journal, regular international conferences and the activity of Task Groups and Working Groups.

Data Science Journal

CODATA curates the [Data Science Journal](#), an important venue for the research data community. The journal is hosted by Ubiquity Press; Mark Parsons and Matt Mayernik are the joint Editors-in-Chief. Since the move to Ubiquity Press in 2014/15, the Data Science Journal has shown steady progress against a number of metrics (impact factor, citations, H-Index, number of articles published). In September 2021, DSJ implemented a long-overdue increase in its APC: this was required to cover costs, but will also increase the fund for APC waivers and provide resource to assist the Editorial Board with promoting the journal. DSJ remains an important service that CODATA provides to the data community, an accessible, quality journal at relatively low cost, that deals with the science of data.

International Data Week / SciDataCon

The main conference to which CODATA now contributes is International Data Week. IDW comprises SciDataCon (a research conference organised by CODATA and the World Data System) and the RDA's Plenary Meeting. Past editions are [IDW 2016 Denver - SciDataCon Programme](#) and [IDW 2018 Gaborone - SciDataCon Programme](#).

Virtual SciDataCon 2021

Following the postponement of International Data Week to June 2022, CODATA and WDS held [Virtual SciDataCon 2021, 18-28 October - Virtual SciDataCon Programme](#). The event provided a notable opportunity for some initiatives, Task Groups and projects to showcase their progress. Themes included: [Core Interoperability](#); [Data for SDGs and DRR](#); [Global Open Science Infrastructures](#); [Open Science and Data Policy](#); [Data Repositories and Stewardship](#); [Earth Sciences Data](#); [Data Skills and Stewardship](#); [Supporting FAIR Research](#); and [strategic sessions for the CODATA and WDS Communities](#). The event was a considerable success with over 1300 attendees across the two weeks. We are grateful for sponsorship from SpringerNature which helped cover the extra costs of running the event without a registration fee, ensuring better global access.

International Data Week 2022, hybrid and Seoul, Republic of Korea

The [next International Data Week will be held in a hybrid virtual and onsite format, in Seoul, Republic of Korea on 20-23 June](#). The call for sessions for the SciDataCon component has been released with a [deadline of 14 February 2022](#).

IDW 2023 and 2025

IDW 2023 will take place in [Salzburg, 23–26 October](#). The Call for Proposals for IDW 2025 is open with a deadline 31 January 2022.

CODATA Conferences

CODATA has run an international conference (roughly biennially) [since 1968](#). Since 2014, CODATA has collaborated with WDS on [SciDataCon](#). Nevertheless, a number of CODATA Conferences have been run with National Members since.

- CODATA 2017, Saint Petersburg, Russia
- [CODATA 2019, Towards Next-Generation Data-Driven Science 2019, Beijing, China](#)

RDM in Institutions 2018-2019

In 2018-2019 CODATA organised a series of large workshops on RDM in Institutions.

- [Göttingen-CODATA RDM Symposium 2018](#), Göttingen, Germany (with Göttingen University)
- [Drexel-CODATA FAIR-RRDM Workshop 2019](#), Philadelphia, USA (with Drexel University)
- [CODATA-Helsinki Workshop on FAIR RDM in Institutions 2019](#), Helsinki, Finland (with the Finnish National Committee)

VizAfrica 2019

In 2019, CODATA assisted with the [second VizAfrica Conference, in Gaborone, Botswana](#). It is intended that this should continue as a series, but the pandemic has put this aspiration on hold.

FAIR Convergence Symposium, 2020 and 2022

In partnership with GO FAIR, the [first fully virtual FAIR Convergence Symposium](#) was held from 27 Nov-4 Dec 2020. This partnership was a great success with over 1100 participants and very good feedback. It enabled both teams to learn a lot, very quickly, about running virtual conferences!

The second FAIR Convergence Symposium is planned for 24-28 October 2022, in Leiden, co-located with the first FDO Conference.

Data Science Task Groups

A number of CODATA TGs address fundamental issues in data science.

Task Group on Fundamental Physical Constants

CODATA's longstanding and foundational contribution to global science is convening the [TG on Fundamental Physical Constants](#). The TG is also supported by the BIPM and the [CODATA recommended values \(reflecting the 2018 adjustment\)](#) now [underpin the SI System](#). The TGFC performs ongoing work of fundamental importance and therefore, since 2016, was given the status of a standing Task Group.

Task Group on Fundamental Physical Constants: Next Steps

The September 2021 TGFC was held in conjunction with the meeting of the BIPM Consultative Committee for Units (20 to 24 September), hosted by the BIPM. Preparations are being made for the 2022 adjustment (data to be used must be published or discussed in a preprint prior to 31 December 2022).

The TGFC was awarded the CODATA prize at the Gaborone GA. A (belated) award ceremony will be held at IDW 2022 in Seoul. [An MoU has been agreed with BIPM](#) to formalise the relationship and support for the TGFC.

Task Group on advanced mathematical tools for data-driven applied systems analysis

The purpose of the Task Group is to explore advanced mathematical tools and apply systems analysis to the consideration of a range of applied challenges. The TG convened a [two-day workshop at IIASA, Laxenburg, Austria in February 2020](#). This led directly to the publication, in March 2021, of a book of articles [Resilience in the Digital Age](#). The TG has helped CODATA develop a closer collaboration with IIASA and was instrumental in convening an important [panel session on Big Data, FAIR Data, Open Data](#) as part of the Systems Analysis in Eurasia conference in April 2021. The TG organised a session at Virtual SciDataCon 2021 on [Data Science and Systems Analysis](#).

Task Group on advanced mathematical tools for data-driven applied systems analysis: next steps

The TG applied for renewal and has presented plans for 2021-2023. These include a webinar on 'Big Data and Knowledge Engineering convergence: Extending the mathematical background of Systems Analysis' in September-October 2021; a second TG Workshop on 'Big Data and Systems Analysis' to be held at the Geophysical Centre of Russian Academy of Sciences or virtually in April 2022; and a webinar on 'Incomplete Data and Systems Analysis', February 2023. The TG aims to publish the workshop proceedings as an OA book with [IntechOpen](#) in 2022.

Task Group on Improving Data Access and Reusability (IDAR-TG)

The [IDAR TG](#) was conceived as a way of re-engaging with issues of data preservation, data rescue following the end of the previous TG in that space. In the early life of the new TG, the co-chairs aimed to raise awareness and attended a number of meetings to that end. However, more than other TGs, and as a new TG, the co-chairs found it difficult to adapt to the circumstances of the pandemic. Nevertheless, the TG is now preparing an article on 'Improving Data Access and Reusability: The Rights and Responsibilities of Researchers'. The TG has applied for renewal and has organised a session at Virtual SciDataCon 2021 to launch a new, more practical and early-career focused approach: '[Data on the Brink: An Unconference / Do-A-Thon](#)'.

4: Data Skills

CODATA convenes a number of activities around data skills and data education.

CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science

One of the most significant activities in the area of data skills and education since 2016 has been the [CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science](#). This joint CODATA-RDA activity developed a core, foundational curriculum of data skills of utility to early career researchers in all fields. This is given in a two-week, intensive training activity or 'school': [an impressive series of events has been run since 2016](#). In 2021 the team organised two virtual schools: one run from [South Africa \(3 May to 9 July\)](#) and another run from [ICTP in Trieste \(September-November\)](#).

The Data Schools team organised a session at Virtual SciDataCon 2021 on [Building Learning Communities](#).

FAIRsFAIR Project

CODATA is part of the FAIRsFAIR project. The major contributions include 1) the CODATA-RDA Data Schools, which developed an additional data stewardship curriculum and have delivered this through [a series of in-person and online events](#); 2) the Competence Centre, including the organisation and curation of the training materials and their annotation using Terms4FAIRskills (see below).

Beijing Data Science Training Workshop Series

In partnership with CODATA China and CNIC, CODATA has run [a series of Data Science Training Workshops](#) (2019, 2017, 2016, 2014, 2012) for early career researchers from LMICs. The training courses generally cover some aspects of the 'Data Schools' curriculum, additional material relating to data policy and CODATA activities, as well as activities based around expertise of partner Chinese research institutes (e.g. CNIC, RADI) and visiting scholars (the Training Workshops have often been organised to coincide with a CODATA event, allowing us to involve international experts).

The Training Workshops led to similar activities in other countries ([Nairobi, 2014](#); [Bangalore, 2015](#); [Jakarta, 2015](#); Antananarivo, 2017), sometimes in partnership with other initiatives or TGs. They have also been instrumental, with the CODATA-RDA Data Schools, in developing our early career network.

Israel Academy Data Education Workshop

With the National Academies of Sciences and Humanities in Israel, CODATA has been planning a substantial workshop to review data science curriculum development in relation to the requirements of undergraduates, of postgraduates, and of researchers in a range of disciplines. The workshop is intended to mark the publication of a National Academies report on this topic, chaired by previous CODATA vice president Niv Ahituv. The event has been repeatedly delayed due to the pandemic, but the intention remains to pursue this activity, perhaps through a workshop or through a Task Group. The organisers have proposed a session for International Data Week 2022 on 'Education for Data Science'.

CASRAI RDM Terminology

CASRAI was a Canadian-based membership organisation that developed and maintained a number of terminologies of significance to academia, Open Access and research

data management. One of the most important and widely used CASRAI products was the [RDM Glossary](#), which had its roots in work by Research Data Canada. In 2016 and 2017, CODATA partnered with CASRAI on an activity to expand, refine and internationalise the Glossary and co-convened a WG which performed a number of 'review cycles' using the CASRAI approach (experts review the vocabulary, select a subset of terms to refine/improve or terms to add, conduct the work and then put the results out for public review, after which the terminology is modified and the review cycle closed for another period). When CASRAI ended operations in 2020, CODATA was asked to steward the renamed RDM Glossary.

The CASRAI RDM Terminology has now been relaunched and the guidance of the 10 Simple Rules to Make a Vocabulary FAIR will be applied. [CODATA invited applications to participate in the Working Group](#) to review, update and refine the terminology, using the review cycle process. The WG was initiated in November 2021 and will be chaired and managed by Laura Molloy (CODATA).

Terms4FAIRskills

The Terms4FAIRskills activity has its origins in a series of workshops that were organised, with a number of partners, including GO FAIR and FAIRsharing, to explore training requirements. Among the requirements identified was the need for a consistent terminology of skills and competences required in the process of making data FAIR. Such a terminology would have a number of uses: underpinning consistent descriptions of curricula, learning outcomes, skills requirements in employment etc. The activity was scoped in a workshop in May 2019 and then [successfully applied for EOSC Co-Creation Funding](#). The technical report for the Terms4FAIRskills project is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772741>. Following the model of the CASRAI RDM Terminology, Terms4FAIRskills will be curated through a periodic working group and review cycle process, convened by CODATA and the other partners, and co-chaired by Laura Molloy (CODATA) and Peter McQuilton (formerly FAIRsharing).

CODATA Connect

The [CODATA Connect Early Career and Alumni Network](#) has been one of the most active and successful activities in 2019-2020. The group comprises alumni from the CODATA-RDA Data Schools and the Training Workshops, as well as ECRs involved in other CODATA activities (for example, the ECR members of the Citizen Science TG).

Among the notable successes of the CODATA Connect team have been the two podcast series already mentioned above

([Data-Knowledge-Action for Urban Systems, 2021](#); [Data for Resilient Cities, 2020](#)) and the [2020 Webinar Series on Smart and Resilient Cities](#). Additionally, in 2020, CODATA Connect ran a very successful and well attended series of [webinars on Research Skills](#), as well as an [ECR essay competition in the Data Science Journal](#).

In 2021, CODATA Connect partnered with the CODATA-RDA Data Schools on a new webinar series on [Research Skills Enhancement](#), focusing on refining skills contained in the Data Schools curriculum. A [workshop introducing the basics of Spark in R and how to easily include lazy evaluation in a data analysis workflow](#) was organised in June 2021.

PASTD TG

The '[Preservation of and Access to Scientific and Technical Data in/for/with Developing Countries Task Group](#)' is, after TGFC, the second longest running CODATA Task Group. The TGs activities have focussed on data publication (promoting the [Global Change Research](#)

[Data and Publishing Repository](#), including for 2020 a [COVID-19 Knowledge and Data Hub](#)) and on training in research skills and research data management. Recent training activities include:

- International Training Workshop on Earth Observation for Sustainable Development in Developing Countries, Beijing, China, 18-30, October, 2020 with ICIMOD, UNESCAP
- Software training on Snow Cover Dynamics and Glacier Fluctuations in the Himalaya, 7-8 March 2020, supported by IGU Commission on Biogeography and Biodiversity
- The IGU Young and Early Career Geographers' Taskforce (IGU-YECG) organized a series of activities at 2018 International Geographical Union (IGU) Regional Conference.

The PASTD TG organized [a session summarising its activities](#) for Virtual SciDataCon 2021.

5: CODATA Secretariat

Over the last 2-3 years, CODATA has managed to increase resources and therefore increase the capacity of its Secretariat.

The Secretariat now comprises (not all FTE equivalent):

Sally Davies, Secretariat Assistant: office administration and finances.

Arofan Gregory, Metadata and Technical Consultant, Decadal Programme.

Simon Hodson, Executive Director

Asha Law, Programme Assistant: communications, technical platforms and website.

Laura Molloy, Senior Research Lead: FAIRsFAIR project, vocabularies and terminologies, Terms4FAIR skills, project and research development.

Hana Pergl, Operations Manager: strategic and management activities, membership relations, GOSC.

*After very kindly extending her support for CODATA during the pandemic, **Sally Davies** (right) will be leaving CODATA to enjoy her overdue retirement from 2022.*

CODATA is very grateful for all Sally's work for CODATA since 2012!

CODATA Project Teams

Over the last 2-3 years the following expert colleagues have contributed to CODATA activities through various forms of project work.

Simon Cox, FAIR Vocabularies, CSIRO-funded CODATA project (completed).

Jay Greenfield, INSPIRE (completed) and INSPIRE-PEACH (ongoing).

Arofan Gregory, DDI-CDI for EOSC (completed), INSPIRE (completed) and INSPIRE-PEACH (ongoing).

Yann Le Franc, terms4FAIRskills (completed).
LI Aitong, GBIF Review Project (completed); CASEarth Review Project (ongoing).
Peter McQuilton, terms4FAIRskills (completed).
Bill Michener, GBIF Review Project (completed).
Hans Pfeiffenberger, GBIF Review Project (completed).
Paul Uhlir, GBIF Review Project (completed); CASEarth Review Project (ongoing).
Joachim Wackerow, DDI-CDI for EOSC (completed).
Joseph Muliaro Wafula, GBIF Review Project (completed).

CODATA Volunteers

Notwithstanding, the increase in CODATA effort through additional secretariat and project resources, CODATA fundamentally relies on volunteer or seconded effort from Task Group co-chairs and members and from its [Executive Committee and Officers](#). Considerable recognition and gratitude are due to these dedicated members of the CODATA Community.

*The 2021 General Assembly sees four outgoing members of the Executive Committee. This includes Simon Cox (ExComm member since 2018) and Joseph Muliaro Wafula (ExComm member since 2016): we are grateful for their valuable contributions. **Bonnie Carroll** (below left, outgoing Secretary General, ExComm member since 2012, Secretary General since 2016) and **John Broome** (below right, outgoing Treasurer, ExComm member since 2010, Treasurer since 2012) deserve particular recognition for their long service.*

